

Impact of Advertisement on Buying Behaviours of the consumers: Study of Cosmetic Industry in Karachi City.

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Abstract

Advertisements have been used for many years to influence the buying behaviors of the consumers. Advertisements are helpful in creating the awareness and perception among the customers of cosmetic products; both of these variables are lethal combination to influence the buying behaviors of the consumers. This particular research was conducted on the 200 young male or female who use different brands of cosmetics to check the influence of advertisement on their buying behavior while creating the awareness and building the perceptions. Correlation and regression analysis were used to identify the relationship between these variables. The results revealed provide the new way to managers to devise suitable strategy for the marketing of cosmetic products. These results show that advertisements are very useful in creating the awareness among the people but they are failed to build strong perceptions in the mind of consumers. Both of these variables such as consumer awareness and consumer perceptions will motivate the consumer to buy a certain product, as there is a positive relationship present in between them.

1. Introduction

The cosmetic industry in Pakistan is growing rigorously in last few years. Although Pakistan's local products have less demand as compared to the international brands. The increasing of cosmetic products is due to the reason that people are bombarded with the advertisements through which they gather information and this factor motivate them to purchase it. Cosmetic industry is directly related with the fashion industry as consumers have the deep insight about their looks and the fashion trending at specific time. Person's desire to look good and be acceptable in the society highly influences the people to buy the cosmetic products.

This particular thesis focuses on the advertisement and various spending of advertisements on different factors of consumer buying behavior. Consumer buying behavior is mostly affected by some factors which include culture, family and brand image. On the other hand brand awareness also helps the customer to buy a certain product. Due to this fact, cosmetic companies focus on advertising the products. This report also put light on other factors which cal also influence the buying behavior of the consumers such as life styles, purchasing power, technology, traditional culture and income. Advertisers spend much amount of investment while advertising their product so they keep their focus on these factors so that they can influence consumer mind with advertisements.

This research also put the light on the buying behavior of customers. Perceptions of the brands and buying behaviors usually change from person to person. So it is important to find out the consumer behavior changes.

Advertisement helps the company to create the awareness in their customers and ingredients the advertisements shape the perception of the customers either in the positive or in a negative way. People can perceive the quality of the products by gathering the information which they usually get through advertisements. The perception of the quality, awareness of the product and consumer opinion drives the consumer buying decision. Study critically evaluates these factors which shape the buying behavior and provides the deep insights towards the role of advertisements shaping the consumer behavior.

1.1.Problem Statement:

As companies are spending large amount of investment on the advertisement because they want to keep their product at the top of the customer's mind. Advertisement has proven to be a successful tool for the

communication but companies are still in the confusion that what kind of ingredients should be there and how do these advertisements will help to change the consumer buying behavior.

1.2.Research Questions:

How does advertisement create awareness in consumers?

Do advertisements build perceptions in the mind of consumers?

Does consumer awareness and perception affect their buying behavior?

1.3.Research Objectives:

To identify the impact of advertisement on consumer awareness

To identify the role of advertisement on building consumer perception

To study the impact of consumer awareness and perception on buying behavior

1.4.Significance of the study:

This particular research focuses on the impact of advertisement on the user's behavior. It explores the factors which are affected by the advertisement and ultimately influence the buying behavior of the consumers. The study will help the readers to understand the consumer behavior while purchasing the cosmetic products so that they can devise appropriate strategy to advertise their product in a best possible way.

1.5.Scope of the study:

The conclusions drawn from the study are based on the responses given by the consumers in a specific area. This study will be helpful in getting an insight into the perception of Consumers on Advertisements and its impacts on changing the buying behaviors of consumers.

1.6.Limitations of the study:

During the study time was the major constraint faced by the researcher, due short time period researcher cover the behaviors of the people at a particular time. The other limitation in this research was of limited area as this research comprises only in the Karachi premises so it does not represent the whole population. The third limitation was resources prohibited to take the large sample size and the fourth limitation was brands chosen for this research were limited.

2. Literature Review

In the present era, marketers are focusing customer rule that is customer is their first preference. To keep deep eye on customers the primary responsibility to the organization is to gain the knowledge about the customers. In this way marketers will be successful in fulfilling the needs and wants of the customers and seek the better opportunities in the market. Researchers find out that marketers need to understand these four things in order to serve their customers better. Firstly marketers must know that customers make rational decisions so they can get the best product available in the market. Secondly customers also make irrational decisions and they are very impulsive and can be attracted towards the promotional activities. In the same way emotional association also put an influence on the mind of customers. In the last customers also buy as a problem solver, they seek the products which can solve their problem (Gupta, 2013)

2.1.Advertisement and factors influencing:

Advertisement is an attempt at creativity which influences the consumer's motive to buy a particular product and change or make the perception of the product in the mind of the consumers. Advertisement appeal act as a supplier to arouse the psychological motive of the consumer for buying. Advertisement involves rational and emotional appeals. In rational appeals the product can be emphasized mainly on its benefits and the problems

which it can solve while on the other hand emotional appeal meet the consumer's psychological, emotional and social requirements (GUNJAN BAHETI, 2012).

Rafique et al, 2012 argued that advertisement is a way to communicate with the audience. They believed that culture highly influence the buying behaviors of the people because every person has different wants and trends according to their life styles. Thus if we say that advertisement is like a magic than it will not be false because advertisement actually changes the needs and wants of the people and sometimes it creates the need among the people (Yasir Rafique, 2012). People are highly affected by the advertisements and organizations are trying to target the masses of the people. Organizations are using above the line and below the line techniques of the advertisement which fit best with their products. Researchers have found that media advertisement are most popular advertisements and people like television ads, so it is a suitable medium to advertise products like cosmetics and FMCG.

A research conducted in India found that adolescents are highly attracted towards the TV commercial. Along with that teen girls also influenced by the TV commercials and they tend to buy the products which they saw in commercials. So it gives us idea that mass media has the great impact on the advertisements. Organizations are moving towards the creative content which attracts the teenage girls as well as boys to buy the products (Nidhi Kotwal, 2008).

With the modern era there has been seen a remarkable boom in technology, with this technology advertisers now considering the number of mass media channels and means of communications which provide them the easy and fast access to the consumers. Other side of this technology advancement is that customers are now having plenty of information and they can get the thing which best suits to them. So it becomes very difficult for the advertiser to build the brand awareness and condition the mind of the customers to make final purchase decision, as customers are gaining more control over the products and information (Raju, 2013).

2.2.Consumer attitude and behaviors

As mentioned earlier, consumer buying pattern is directly evolved from the consumer behavior and its attitude. Many things combine to build up the behavior of any individual. The first thing which influences the consumer behavior and shapes it is his culture. Culture builds the strong perceptions of the products in the mind of the customers (hye-Shin Kim, 2008). According to Rai, 2013, there are several national and international brands which people recognized and have strong perception in their minds. These perceptions are pinched in their mind because of their culture, life styles and surroundings. Also advertisements have very important role in shaping the consumer behavior. Advertisements are the source of motivation which forces them to buy a particular product. Advertisements are also a source of building trust. Consumer is induced significantly if he is looking for the quality and prices of the products. Purchase attitude can also be build up by product evaluation and brand recognition (Rai, 2013).

Consumers in all over the world are attracted towards the brand and products which are emotionally attached with their behaviors. Studies found that emotional attachments put a huge influence on the customers and their buying behavior as people tend to associate themselves with the brand.

Advertisements shape the behaviors of the people through cognition. Cognition is the perception of a person towards the information communicated through advertisements. These cognitions are observed by the individual through his senses, perception, attention, memory, reasoning, language, etc. best way of attracting the customers is to understand the psychological cognitive aspects of the consumers (Sandra Jakštienė, 2008).

2.3.Impact of Advertisement

Role of advertisement is to carry message to the far distances. It is also use to target the scatter mass audience. The role of advertising on sales volume is very important. It is proved to be very essential tool in enhancing the sales of brand. Advertisement is directly linked with the sales of the products (Abiodun, 2011).

Through advertisements customer behavior shaped and they motivate to buy such products. Researchers found that repetition in the advertisement hit the mind of the customers which also help them to remember that product and purchase repeatedly (Pope, 2009).

2.4.Domestic Cosmetic Industry

Domestic market of Pakistan has been growing rigorously over the couple of decades. The range of the cosmetics and beauty products are widening with a good pace. Some local companies start manufacturing the cosmetic product to fulfill the domestic as well as international need. This industry is growing and have potential due to two reasons, first the effective cost cut and cheap available in the Pakistan market and second is the increasing purchasing power of the people of the country. The demand of the cosmetic products is increasing due to advance media and massive advertisements on the media. People start considering these products as essential of the life. But due to all of these facts the total spending of the Pakistan's individual is very less as compared to the overall average spending per person in world. Industry has much potential in it and can contribute much in the economy of country, however in present time it is highly fragmented and concentrated in big cities (Fazal ur Rehman, 2014)

2.5.Consumer buying behavior of Cosmetic products:

According to the surveys conducted, this market is highly competitive in nature and mainly comprises on the female with the males as par with them. Consumer is considered as a king of market and marketers are focusing on the different factors to attract more and more customers. These factors include the buying habits, preferences, taste, like and dislikes of consumers and accordingly they need to revise its policies and marketing mix. As we see the buying behavior of consumers of this market it is obvious that people are highly quality conscious. People are highly associated with the brand due to quality and results of the specific brand. They are attached emotionally with the brands and they can wait for the product during the non availability of the product. Although people are becoming brand conscious but the actual brand decision is in their hands (Desai, 2014).

2.6.Strategic innovation in cosmetic industry

Practitioners and strategists think that strategic innovation is an inclusive term which involves the different innovation and creativity like new products and services. The companies are expanding due to saturation of the local markets and these companies are going internationally and globally. Several strategic innovation must be taken into account for these kind of expansions. Strategic innovation involves four things that are new market creation, product value addition, competitive disruption and service value addition (Caroline SueLin, 2010). Cosmetic industry is focusing in these four dimensions. Cosmetics are not essential in the life of human beings yet they have to create their market and expand their circle. So they have to focus on these things. They can attract the customers by providing the best services and assuring the quality. Marketers in the cosmetic industry are continuously finding ways to bring new and innovative products for their customers. Along with this they are also focusing on making the most attractive and appealing advertisements, so that they can attract more and more customers (Xu Yang, 2012).

2.7.GMS model in Cosmetic Industry

Global marketing strategies are very crucial and sensitive area for which managers has to take responsible step before entering into the new and existing markets.

Cosmetic companies are making the standardized products for the consumers all over the world. This gives them way to create the strong brand image and personality in the mind of the customers. With the analysis of some global cosmetic companies like Chanel and Guerlain are making the standardized products for the all over the world. Companies launch the products three to four times in a year. As we have seen that cosmetic companies are offering the same products with little or minimum changes all over the world. Companies do so for attaining the economies of the scales and ensuring the quality. Along with that, companies also follow the

localization strategy, in order to penetrate in the new market. Marketers represent their strategies in their advertisements. In cosmetics advertising is very important in creating the brand. For this they are using the stars and celebrities from Hollywood and Bollywood in their commercials (Ivančová, 2013). While analyzing these commercials it is obvious that cosmetics companies target the elite class and arouse the desire in them to own the product even these are not accessible in market. Companies want to spread the same brand image all over the world so they are showing the standardized commercials all over the world (Ivančová, 2013)

2.8. Attitudes toward cosmetic products:

Attitudes are formed through experience and learning and that attitude influence the buying behavior. The positioning of the brand is dependent on the success and failure of the company. Middle aged people have positive attitude towards the cosmetics and beauty products because they want to look young and also they are settled in their life so they have spending to spend on these luxuries (Tamizhjothi, 2013)

Along with the women, men are also arriving in the world of cosmetics. Although common men are reluctant in using the creams and beauty products but still they are now attracting towards this industry. Interest of men in the cosmetics arises due to care of their body and face impression. The competition in the professional world put influence on the men to care for their looks.

Several factors influence on the men attitudes to shape the behavior. These factors include environmental factors, socio demographic factors and economical factors. In environmental factors culture, social class and group or family influences the attitude of the men and in socio demographic factors age and location are the key factors which influence on the buying behavior of the men (BLANCHIN Audrey).

2.9. Techniques used in advertisements

Several types of techniques are used in the advertisements and promotion of the cosmetics. Some of them are explained (OAKLEY, 2009):

- 2.9.1. Aspirational advertisement: This type of advertisement is most successful in young age people. This kind of advertisement involves the slogans and tag lines which inspire them. For example “most beautiful me” and “true perfection has to be imperfect”. Aspirational advertisements are mainly based on three pillars that are perfection, sex appeal and status (OAKLEY, 2009).
- 2.9.2. Celebrity Endorsement: this kind of advertisement is very important and successful in all age group especially young people. Using the celebrity may enhance the trust of the people to buy product but it is not evident that this kind of advertisement also provides brand loyalty (OAKLEY, 2009).
- 2.9.3. Social responsibility advertisements: like dove many cosmetics brand are associated with the benefits of the society. According to survey women wearing cosmetic feel confident because these brands advertise them as providing the confident in the society (OAKLEY, 2009).

Along with these kinds of advertisement strategies, brands have various slogans which influence the buying behavior of the customers all over the world. Brands use these slogans cross culturally. In the world numbers of slogans are used in English and French languages to enhance the brand validity, brand appeals, brand positives and brand philosophies (Ringrow).

3. Research Methodology

3.1. Hypothesis:

Four hypotheses have been developed in this research article.

H₀: There is no relationship between advertisement and consumer awareness

H₁: There is a relationship between advertisement and consumer awareness

H₀: There is a relationship between advertisement and consumer perception

H₂: There is a relationship between advertisement and consumer perception

H₀: Consumer awareness and consumer perception have no impact on buying behavior

H₃: Consumer awareness and consumer perception have impact on buying behavior

3.2. Research Model:

Following is the research model given

In the proposed model it clearly examines the impact of advertisement on the consumer buying behavior.

The advertisement has the direct impact on the consumer despite of the cost. It creates the awareness in the consumer thus motivate them to buy the product. Along with that advertisement also build the positive or negative perception about the bands. Our research model identifies the impact of advertisements on customer awareness and perception which leads towards the buying decision of the consumer. This model firstly tells the factors which can influence on the consumer buying behavior and secondly it helps to adopt the right way of using the advertisement for male and female keeping in mind the factors of awareness and perception which will ultimately fulfill the needs of consumer and enhance their desire to purchase a specific product and motivate customers to repurchase these products.

3.3. Data Collection and Analysis:

3.3.1. Research Approach:

In this particular research quantitative approach has been used and the data was the primary one gathered from the users of cosmetics products in Karachi.

3.3.2. Research Instrument

A questionnaire was developed to gather the data from the respondents. Likert's scale was used in the questionnaire. A survey was conducted in various places of city to gather the primary data from the users of cosmetic industry. The data gathered from the authentic source and it was clearly defined to them that this response will only be using in research purpose.

3.3.3. Sample Size:

A size of 200 respondents was taken under consideration. Sample will be taken in the premises of Karachi city.

3.3.4. Statistical Tools and Analysis:

The data gathered from the respondents were put in the SPSS to analyze the various factors and dependability of the variables.

4. Data Analysis and Discussion

Buying is a complex process which involves series of decisions and important questions such as what to buy, where to buy, when to buy and how to buy. These series of decisions drive from the consumer awareness and consumer perceptions. Buyers aware of the product through one source or multiple sources have more information regarding the brand and the product. In our research we consider the advertisement as a basic source of creating awareness in the mind of customers. The main reason behind the creating awareness in the mind of the customers is the content and information used in the particular advertisement. In the same way content of the advertisements also build the perceptions of the customers who are watching these advertisements. The results of our research depict that advertisements are the main source of creating awareness as well as shaping the perceptions of the customers. Consumer awareness and consumer perceptions are considered as the two main drivers that lead towards the buying decisions.

4.1. Sample Characteristics

In the figure 1, age of the respondents shown. In our random sampling the major portion which was influenced by the advertisements lies in between 18 years to 23 years. Along with that significant amount of respondents are also attracted towards the advertisements whose age lie within 24 to 29 years.

Figure 1: Age of the respondents

In the figure 2, we showed income level of our respondents which are attracted towards the advertisements of cosmetics. Results show that the people having adequate amount of income are also more responsive to the advertisements as compared to the low income individuals. In our sample size mostly people have income lies between 25000 to 60000. They are middle class people who watch advertisements to gain the information and make suitable decisions while purchasing the cosmetic brand.

In our research three hypothesis were tested on the data collected from our respondents. These hypothesis were related to impact of advertisements in creating awareness and perception of customers. At the end impact of both awareness and perception on buying behavior were analyzed.

4.2.Hypothesis Analysis

Hypothesis 1:

H₀: there is no relationship between advertisement and consumer awareness

H₁: there is a relationship between advertisement and consumer awareness

Our first hypothesis was to analyze the relationship between advertisements and consumer awareness. As advertisement is the source of information which creates awareness in the mind of the customers and is useful in introducing the new product.

Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Advertisement	2.2700	.63262	200
Consumer_Awareness	2.0675	.63883	200

Correlations

		Advertisement	Consumer_Awareness
Advertisement	Pearson Correlation	1	.162*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.011
	Sum of Squares and Cross-products	79.642	13.022
	Covariance	.400	.065
	N	200	200
Consumer_Awareness	Pearson Correlation	.162*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.011	
	Sum of Squares and Cross-products	13.022	81.214
	Covariance	.065	.408
	N	200	200

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

In the above hypothesis we applied the correlation test through SPSS on our 200 sample size. The results show that significance level of the test is 0.011 which is less than 0.05 which means that our null hypothesis will be rejected such as there is no relationship between advertisements and the customer awareness. From our results

we can conclude that there is a relationship present between the advertisements and consumer awareness. Pearson correlation value shows us that both variables have positive relationship with each other. Although the value of Pearson correlation is less which means that relationship between these two variables is not so strong but still there is a positive relationship present in between them.

Hypothesis 2

H₀: there is a relationship between advertisement and consumer perception

H₂: there is a relationship between advertisement and consumer perception

In our second hypothesis we try to find out the relationship between the advertisements and the consumer perception. It is important to check the relationship between advertisements and consumer perception.

Results of this hypothesis test are given below:

Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Advertisement	2.2700	.63262	200
Consumer_Perception	2.1890	.66414	200

Correlations

		Advertisement	Consumer_Perception
Advertisement	Pearson Correlation	1	-.030
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.339
	Sum of Squares and Cross-products	79.642	-2.473
	Covariance	.400	-.012
	N	200	200
Consumer_Perception	Pearson Correlation	-.030	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.339	
	Sum of Squares and Cross-products	-2.473	87.776
	Covariance	-.012	.441
	N	200	200

The significance level of this test comes out 0.339 which is far more than 0.05, it means that we are failed to reject the null hypothesis which was there is no relationship between advertisements and consumer perception in the cosmetic industry. In cosmetic industry people do not only rely on the advertisements on building their

perceptions and they believe more on the trial of the products. On the other hand people also listen from their peer and friends and build some perceptions. Thus there are many other options which help in building the perceptions in the mind of the customers but advertisements is not an option for building the perception in the mind of the customers. Human beings do not build the positive or negative perception by just watching the product they will try to use those products at least one time while building any perception in their mind. Experience is the major driver of building the perceptions because of this fact most of the cosmetics companies are using tool of sales promotions along with the advertisements in which they give free trial or sample product to the customers to use. The aim behind these sales promotions is to provide the experience to their customers, this help them to build the perception of their product.

Hypothesis 3

H₀: Consumer awareness and consumer perception have no impact on buying behavior.

H₃: Consumer awareness and consumer perception have impact on buying behavior.

In our third hypothesis we try to find out the existence of the relationship between consumer awareness and perception with the buying behavior of customers. In our research we apply the test on the responses of 200 people residing in the Karachi and using several types of cosmetic products. Results are shown below.

Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Consumer_Buying_Behavior	2.6208	.73630	200
Consumer_Awareness	2.0675	.63883	200
Consumer_Perception	2.1890	.66414	200

Above table shows the means of the 200 responses of people. In this table all of the variables have mean near to 2 which indicates that most of the people agree on the relationship of these variables with each other.

Correlations

		Consumer_Buying_Behavior	Consumer_Awareness	Consumer_Perception
Pearson Correlation	Consumer_Buying_Behavior	1.000	.390	.569
	Consumer_Awareness	.390	1.000	.387
	Consumer_Perception	.569	.387	1.000
Sig. (2-tailed)	Consumer_Buying_Behavior	.	.000	.000
	Consumer_Awareness	.000	.	.000
	Consumer_Perception	.000	.000	.
N	Consumer_Buying_Behavior	200	200	200
	Consumer_Awareness	200	200	200
	Consumer_Perception	200	200	200

In the above table, Pearson correlation values have been shown with respect to each individual. Through this table we can evaluate the impact of one variable on other variables. Such as for the 1 value of the customer awareness it cause increase in value of buying behavior by 0.390.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics		
						R Square Change	F Change	df1
1	.598 ^a	.357	.351		.59324	.357	54.773	2

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	38.553	2	19.277	54.773	.000 ^b
	Residual	69.332	197	.352		
	Total	107.885	199			

a. Dependent Variable: Consumer_Buying_Behavior

b. Predictors: (Constant), Consumer_Perception, Consumer_Awareness

From the ANOVA table it can be seen that significance level is $0.000 < 0.05$ which means that our null hypothesis will be rejected. Results conclude that there is an impact of consumer perception and consumer awareness present on the buying decisions of the people.

From the table of Model Summary we can see the value of R square which is 0.357, it means that although there is relationship present between these two independent variables on the dependent variables but that impact is not so strong as value is much smaller than +1. From this analysis we can also say that there is positive relationship present between the perception and awareness with the buying decision behavior of the people.

From our literature review, we find that awareness and perception are the two main drivers which force customers to buy the particular product. In cosmetic industry people usually buy the products if they know enough about the product or it is recommended by any close person. Along with that several other options are also consider in buying behaviors of the people such as brand consciousness, social class effect, good experiences, suitability or loyalty with the brand. But all of these factors will be applicable when the people have awareness of a particular brand and they also have the positive perceptions in their mind. Advertisements are used to create these factors in the customers but despite of advertisements social circle, peers, friends and family greatly affect the perception.

5. Conclusion

This particular research was conducted to find out the impact of advertisements on the buying behavior of the people in cosmetic industry. Study reveals that there are two important variables which can influence the buying behaviors of the people but these two factors are not solely reason to change the behaviors of the consumers rather they can contributing in changing the behaviors of the consumers. Research was conducted under the premises of the Karachi boundaries and 200 respondents were targeted who use various kinds of cosmetics

products from different brands. Results tell that advertisements are useful in coating the awareness among the consumers. TVCs and billboards are widely used by the different marketing departments of the cosmetic companies which are targeting above the line through these medium. Their ads contain enough information to attract the consumers as well as create the awareness in the mind of the customers. First hypothesis was supposed to check the relationship between the advertisement and the consumer awareness. Results showed that there is relationship present between these two. People get awareness through advertisement regarding the cosmetics. Our second hypothesis was supposed to check the relationship between perception and advertisements. In this we failed to reject the null hypothesis which indicates that there is no relationship present between the advertisements and consumer perceptions. This is because of the fact that advertisements cannot create the perceptions in the mind of the customers. Perception drive from the use of the product mainly and other options include recommendation of the peers, friends, colleagues etc. One thing is also important to mention that users of the cosmetics are very loyal to their brands and they cannot be easily shifted towards other brands. Cosmetics are sensitive products which are used for the skin care and with the aim to look beautiful thus most of the people think that particular brand which they have experienced is suitable to their skin and they don't want to do experiments with their skin, so it is difficult to change the perception of the people with advertisements.

After analyzing these two variables which can be influence by the advertisements we find out the relationship of these two variables with that of buying behavior of the people. In this regards our third hypothesis which has aim that there is relationship present between consumer awareness and perception with that of buying behavior was accepted and we reject null hypothesis. Although the impact of these two variables on the buying behavior was low but still they are two significant variables which can shape the buying behaviors of the consumers while purchasing the cosmetics.

In the end we conclude that cosmetic companies should use attractive and informative content to create the awareness in the consumers and they should not rely on the advertisement for changing the perceptions of the consumers instead they should use new ways of sales promotion or other medium to change the perceptions of the people. It will be easy for any company in cosmetic industry to change the buying behavior of consumer by creating awareness and building strong perception in the mind of their customers.

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